

Automatic game-testing with AI

Multi-task reinforcement learning for automatic game-testing

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Abstract

This work presents a scalable solution to automate game-testing. Traditionally, game-testing has been performed by either human players or scripted Artificial Intelligence (AI) agents. While the first produces the most reliable results, the process of organizing testing sessions is time consuming. On the other hand, scripted AI dramatically speeds up the process, however, the insights it provides are far less useful: these agents' behaviors are highly predictable. The presented solution takes the best of both worlds: the automation of scripted AI, and the richness of human testing by framing the problem within the Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) paradigm. Reinforcement Learning (RL) agents are trained to adapt to any unseen level and present customizable human personality traits: such as aggressiveness, greed, fear, etc. This is achieved exploring the problem from a multi-task RL setting. Each personality trait is understood as a different task which can be linearly combined by the proposed algorithm. Furthermore, since Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) have been used to model the agent's policies, the solution is highly adaptable and scalable. This thesis reviews the state of the art in both automatic gametesting and RL, and proposes a solution to the above-mentioned problem. Finally, promising results are obtained evaluating the solution on two different environments: a simple environment used to quantify the quality of the designed algorithm, and a generic game environment useful to show-case its applicability. In particular, results show that the designed agent is able to perform good on game levels never seen before. In addition, the agent can display any convex combination of the trained behaviors. Furthermore, its performance is as good as if it had been specifically trained on that particular combination.

Keywords

Deep Reinforcement Learning, Multi-Task, Successor Features, GameTesting, Persons

Summary

This work presents a scalable solution for automating spell testing. Traditionellt har speltestning performed by either human players or forprogrammerade agents. Aven om det forstannamnda ger de most reliable results ar processen tidskravande. A andra sidan paskyndar forprogrammerade agenter processen dramakt, men de insikter som de ger ar mycket mindre utilisata: dessa agenter beioungen ar mycket furutsagbara. The presented solutions use the best of two worlds: automationsmojligheten fran forprogrammerade agents as well as the opportunity to simulate the depth of the human tester genome att inrama problemet inom paradigm Deep Forstarkningsinlarning. En agent based on forstarkningsinlarning trains and adapts itself to the previously used game environment and presents adaptive human personality traits: such as aggressiveness, greed, fear... skalbar. Denna rapport ganskar forst den senaste forskningen inom both automatic speltestning and forstarkningsinlarning. Senare presenteras en solution for ovan mentioned problem. Slutligen evaluates solutions in two different environments with good results. The first environment is used to quantify the quality of the designed algorithms. The other is a generic game environment that is useful for applying solutions.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

The continuous growth in terms of size and complexity of modern video games exacerbates the need for reliable and scalable automated testing techniques. Understanding the impact of each design choice is key for game developers to deliver the best user experience. Currently, most testing procedures rely on either hard-coded heuristics or human testers [1]. The former suffering from oversimplification and the latter being both time-consuming and economically costly. This work presents a solution in-between both ideas which attempts to complement the work done by human testers. The main idea is to merge the best of both worlds by artificially simulating human players using RL [2]: the branch of machine learning which studies decision-making problems. This way artificial agents deal with the tedious task of detecting common game glitches, while human testers can focus on experiencing the key mechanics of a more ready game. Human players will give richer feedback on how enjoyable is the game without the burden of identifying, documenting, and reporting general glitches.

1.1 Background

Computer game designers need to be continuously testing their work to ensure it provides the intended experience. Originally, the designers themselves would carry out the testing procedure without much overhead. Subsequently however, as game complexity grew, this approach became prohibitive and game developers started exploring alternative methods.

One of such methods is to rely on dedicated human testers. The metrics generated by a diverse set of players are highly valuable, as they give the exact feedback game designers

desire. Nevertheless, repeatedly creating game builds suitable for user-testing, and recruiting users to conduct evaluation sessions is highly costly. Alternatively, various AI techniques have been explored to automate this process. While it dramatically reduces the associated costs, the obtained metrics are far less valuable: scripted agents are extremely predictable. Furthermore, game developers need to specifically create testing AI for each designed environment.

More recently, with the rise of deep learning, DRL-based algorithms have achieved remarkable performance playing computer games. While RL seems ideal for game-testing, current approaches present several limitations which challenge their application in the gaming industry (see chapter 2). This work studies how RL can be efficiently applied to train agents that play games presenting common human characteristics such as curiosity, fear, or stress.

1.2 Problem

For an artificial agent to be a useful game-tester, it needs to present two main characteristics.

First, the testing system has to be as least of a burden as possible to game designers: it must both require little tuning and rapidly provide the desired metrics for fast iteration. While current RL algorithms are very adaptable to game-like environments, they are not particularly fast to train. To address this issue, this work presents a zero-shot transfer method: the agent is able to directly perform well on unseen environments. Thus, the game designer will make use of a pre-trained model capable of adapting to any newly designed level.

Secondly, the agents need to behave as closely as possible to humans. However, humans present different personalities: for instance, some tend to be more cautious, others are adrenaline seekers while others prefer to explore all map regions. RL presents

a natural way of encoding this rich diversity of play-styles: each behavior can be encoded by a different objective function to maximize. Adrenaline-seeking agents can be rewarded for being exposed to dangerous situations while cautious ones will be rewarded for avoiding them. It would be possible to learn a policy for each specific behavior desired to observe, nevertheless, it would be highly time-consuming. To address this challenge, this work explores how one can simultaneously learn multiple personalities and later combine them. This is achieved by training on a base of "extreme" personalities in such a way that, subsequently, one can get any convex combinations of those. Following up on the previous example, we might train a "fully cautious" agent (one whose main priority is to avoid danger), a "fully adrenaline-seeking" agent (one who looks for dangerous situations), and a "fully exploratory" agent (one who wants to discover as much of the map as possible). Later, we can obtain more realistic behaviors by weighting each "extreme" decision by some weight. Notice that we can think of these "behaviours" as different tasks within a given environment, thus framing the problem within the multi-task framework [3].

1.3 Solution

The proposed testing iteration pipeline is presented in figure 1.1. First, the artificial agent is trained on a wide variety of randomized game levels only on the above-mentioned "extreme" personalities. Training on multiple game levels significantly helps on zero-shot transfer to any unseen level. Furthermore, the devised method only need to train a base of personalities to be able to act according to any convex combination of them. Once trained, the model can be run on any hand-crafted level and collect valuable insights on how each personality combination might interact with the proposed level. If the agent does not act as intended, some changes could be considered in the designed level.

1.4 Scientific and engineering issues

While RL algorithms have achieved high proficiency in domains with simple and known rules [4, 5] they present several limitations [6]. To list a few:

- They are slow: they require a lot of experience before performing good. Unlike biological beings, artificial agents have no prior information on the environment around them, making it extremely slow to learn how to behave [7].
- They are brittle: unlike in supervised learning, the data used to train RL algorithms is dependent on the algorithm itself. This can generate a negative feedback loop. A poorly performing agent which does not explore enough will have a much harder time discovering promising

Figure 1.1 – Proposed level-testing pipeline. First, the agent is pre-trained on randomized maps, learning how to behave in "extreme" personalities. Later, the learned model can be run on any hand-designed level acting as any "extreme" personality behavior combination in a 0-shot fashion. Based on the obtained results, the game-designer can decide whether to make changes to the level of interest or not.

states. Thus, there is a high risk of becoming unstable and they might be very sensitive to their hyper-parameters. [8]

This thesis mainly tackles the third challenge. First, the artificial agent has to re-use the knowledge gained playing previous levels to successfully solve any unseen level. Re-training from scratch has to be avoided since

it is highly time-consuming. Second, it has to be able to leverage its acquired skills whilst behaving according to different personalities. It has to be able to mimic the diversity of play-styles presented by human testers.

1.5 Purpose

The main purpose of this work is to explore efficient ways to integrate RL into game testing. This helps game-developers to make more principled design choices at a much time and cost effective way. Likewise, beyond game-testing, game development can benefit enormously from research done in the field of DRL. Currently, most in-game AI implementations rely on simple heuristics over fixed action primitives. DRL opens up the possibilities for an unprecedented degree of realism and unpredictability for non-player characters. This will yield much more natural environments which will become more enjoyable for players. In addition, game developers will not need to hand-design all non-player characters behaviors as they will be automatically learned. Achieving faster, more robust agents capable of leveraging their past experiences to rapidly acquire new skills is essential for its success.

1.6 Motivation

While DRL is progressing at a vertiginous pace, it is still unready for many real-world applications such as robotics. It is yet extremely hard for machines to make sense of the chaotic environment we live in. Effective knowledge re-usability would dramatically enhance their capacity to adapt to unseen environments. Computer games are the perfect test-bed to try out new ideas before bringing them to less structured domains.

1.7 Goals

As previously hinted, this work attempts to explore RL algorithms which assert two key requirements of game-testing:

- Fast adaptation of artificial agents to unseen levels of a particular game: Re-training

the agents from scratch for each game-level is timeconsuming and high compute-resource demanding. Consequently, a pre-trained model which can easily adapt to different game dynamics and maps is desired.

- Capable of displaying different behaviors: Game-designers are interested in capturing how different play-style personalities would behave in the submitted level. Examples of different personalities can be found in table 1.1.

PersonaDescription

Efficient Desire to finish as quickly as possible.

Collectionist Desire to explore all the map and gather as many collectibles as possible.

Cautious Desire to avoid dangerous situations (environmental hazards and enemies).

Reckless Adrenaline-seeking behavior.

Chapter 2

Background

2.1 AI in game-testing

Game-testing is the part of computer game development process which addresses quality control. The more complex computer games become, the more prone they are to present undesirable behaviors, and the harder it is to identify them. As explained in the introduction (see section 1.1), hiring human testers is slow, and can only be done in advanced stages of the game development. Therefore, there have been several attempts to automate this process. This section presents some of the most relevant ones and their main limitations.

presents a study exploring how to use heuristics combined with RL algorithms to design agents that play games providing useful feedback. Furthermore, they experiment on behavioral cloning, competition and collaboration of in-game AI in multiple-agents environments. Nonetheless, their game-testing experiments using RL are quite short and inconclusive. Moreover, they neither address the generality of their approach nor take into consideration different player motivations. This work aims to deal with these limitations taking inspiration from the automated game-testing idea proposed in [1]. Where a game-testing pipeline is directly built within the Unity game engine . They heuristically estimate player’s movements and interactions at the designed level and provide useful visual feedback to the developer. The current work expands on this approach by substituting the hand-crafted behaviors with DRL agents. Our agents perceive the environment very similar

to what the scripted AI in [1] uses to make decisions: by getting the set of visible interactable elements around them (see table 2.1). Regardless of the graphics, one can train our agents to react to these entities and more easily achieve generalization across different games. Thus, the state-space of our MDP [2] will be composed by the type and relative position of the agent’s viewable objects which are tagged/labeled by the game designer. Furthermore, it is easy to simulate different archetypal behaviors (as [1] does) by adjusting the objective function they optimize. For instance, a collectionist agent is more rewarded for gathering collectibles than an efficient agent (see 1.1). This can be seen as a multi-task RL problem: where within the same environment an agent has to learn different tasks (called personalities in this case).

Entity	Description
Final Goal	Objective triggering end of the level.
Optional Goal	Objective not necessary for level completion.
Collectible	Item which can be picked and can benefit the player survival.
Enemy	Hostile character which can reduce health points or restart level.
Environment Hazard	Physical hazard which can harm the player.

Table 2.1 – Game entities examples taken from [1].

2.2 Reinforcement learning

Reinforcement learning is the branch of machine learning which studies decision-making problems. The setup is presented in figure 2.1: an agent interacts with an environment by selecting actions to get as much reward as possible in the long run [2]. The way an agent acts on an environment is defined by a policy function often referred to as π . This interaction is assumed to happen in discrete time-steps and it can be modeled within the formalism of an MDP [17].

An MDP is defined by a tuple $M = (S, A, p, r)$ with the following components:

- **State space** S : Encoding of the environment perceived by the agent.
- **Action space** A : Set of operations an agent can do on the environment. Usually environments are classified into having discrete or continuous actions spaces depending on their nature.
- **Transitions** $p(s^0 | s, a)$: State transition distribution modeling how the state changes when applying an action. Unlike in planning problems, in RL these transitions are assumed to be unknown. Therefore, they are learned by the agent through environment interactions.
- **Reward** $r(s, s^0, a)$: Reward associated with a given transition.

Figure 2.1 – The agent-environment interaction in a MDP [2]

gives the parameters of a policy competent in task j . A common approach is to use a recurrent network to learn a set of parameters characterizing the considered environment .

Other variants attempt to disentangle task

inference and control using a probabilistic approach . Nevertheless, gradient-based approaches such as MAML are the ones which have gained more traction. The idea is to learn the parameters which maximize the expected return of taking a gradient step for each task. Recently, there have been some variants exploring better score function differentiation , better dealing with credit assignment , or introducing a probabilistic framework around it which uses variational inference . The presented problem in this work could be framed within the meta-RL framework. However, after some initial tests using MAML, it was decided to attempt a successor-features approach as they seemed more appropriate for the studie

Chapter 3

Results

3.1 Major results

This chapter analyses qualitatively and quantitatively the designed model on both of the environments considered. First, its performance and generality capabilities are assessed on the clearly distinct tasks defined in the *position reacher environment* 3.1 Later, its usability within a game-testing scenario is measured within the *generic game environment*

3.2 Discussion

Overall, results are promising: the implemented algorithm is able to solve both of the goals originally stated (see section 1.7). It is able to adapt to unseen environments presenting archetypal personality traits with a customizable proportion . Furthermore, the presented solution is much more scalable than previous lines of research (see section 2.1) thanks to the usage of DRL as a general learning framework.

However, from the game-tester perspective, there still are some caveats. First, the game-tester needs to assign tags to each of the relevant entities of the game. Second, it needs to define a routine to randomly generate game levels which resemble the ones willing to be tested. While the first one might not represent a big burden, the implementation of the second one could require some time.

Chapter 4

Conclusions and Future work

4.1 Conclusions

This work tackles the automation of game-testing using DRL. The objective is to have an artificial agent playing the designed game who can automatically provide feedback to the designer. For it to be useful in an industrial setting two key goals were identified. First, adaptation to unseen game levels should be achieved in a 0-shot fashion to allow fast iteration. Second, the agents need to present common human traits (such as aggressiveness, curiosity, or cautiousness) to more realistically cover different play-styles. This thesis presents a scalable algorithm to achieve it within the DRL paradigm. 0-shot transfer is achieved by pre-training the agent on randomized environments. Multiple personalities are achieved by training an action-value function with multiple heads, each of them optimizing a different reward objective. Later, a convex combination of the personalities used in the training can be obtained by linearly combining the learned action-value functions. This approach is first tested on a very simple benchmark environment obtaining promising results. In addition, a generic game environment is developed and used to showcase the potential usage of such a solution for game-testing. The algorithm is able to scale up to this (relatively) more challenging environment and achieves 0-shot transfer while presenting clearly distinct behaviours with meaningful combinations

4.2 Limitations

Because of time constraints, the tested environments are rather simple. Specifically,

the generic game environment does not include all the desired

features initially intended. For instance, it was initially planned to introduce environmental hazards, different type of interactables, and a more intricate way to interact with enemies. However, the advantage of having used ANNs to model the agent policy is that scaling up to more complex environments is fairly simple.

Another important limitation is given by the algorithm used. Q-learning is known to be sample-expensive and brittle. Future lines of work should consider using more recent algorithms to learn the base of tasks.

Finally, it is important to acknowledge that the presented setup requires some work from the game-tester. First, all the relevant game-entities need to be labelled for the artificial agent to recognize. Humans do not need this labelling as previous experience allows them to understand the scene without much interaction. On the counterpart, humans need to have renders of the levels, where artificial agents do not. In addition, the game designed needs to implement some way of randomizing the levels to train on multiple scenarios and be able to generalize to new ones.

4.3 Future work

It is very important to better understand why the SFs approach failed and how to make it work. This would provide a more general framework with the capability of having different policies solving different tasks.

On a different note, it would be interesting to see how the described approach compares to model-based methods both in terms of pre-training time and performance quality. While the multi-task framework really fits the model-based paradigm it would be interesting to see how to deal with randomized environments.

Similarly, it would be helpful to adapt the proposed algorithm to work within the actor-critic framework. Actor-critic algorithms are better suited for continuous control problems and generally outperform value-based ones. Furthermore, to increase the agent's exploration capabilities, it would be interesting to introduce curiosity-based rewards. Experimenting on these lines should help make the solution more scalable to higher complexity environments and thus, more practical.

Reinforcement Learning (IRL) . One could extract behavior patterns from different human players and use them as a reward system for the trained agents.

4.4 Ethics and sustainability considerations

A possible criticism of the presented research could challenge the ethics behind automating this particular step of game-testing. Two main arguments can be done: first, one could posit that game-testing automation can lead to job substitution, second, that training and evaluating artificial agents has a considerable associated carbon footprint. This section further develops on why these arguments are flawed and how it is important that these lines of research are explored.

Regarding the first claim, it is important to keep in mind that the presented solution aims to complement human testing rather than to substitute it. Since artificial agents do not need final rendered game scenes, they can be extremely insightful to assess level design choices in early stages of the game development. This can be useful to more efficiently provide more principled testing cases to human players. Having this extra testing layer before a human session ensures the levels have been carefully designed making the final results much more valuable.

Furthermore, artificial agents and human testers focus on different aspects of game-testing. Artificial agents deal with the repetitive and boring task of detecting and documenting common glitches. If successfully achieved, human testers can then focus on the much more pleasant job of giving feedback on the game experience as a whole. Therefore, both testing procedures complement and improve each other.

Relating to the second claim, one needs to think the long-term benefits of investing in these type of technologies. Effective decision-making AI agents can play a key roll in improving life quality: personalized medical aid, helper robotics, or resource optimization being just some examples of he advantages they can bring. In particular, the energy sector can be vastly optimized using RL techniques. DeepMind's contribution to reducing the energy cost of Google's servers is a great example of what can be achieved with these type of technology. Furthermore, as presented in the introduction (see section 1.5), computer games are a very convenient medium to explore RL algorithms. Experimenting with virtual environments such as computer games is a necessary step towards these benefits.

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